

Clinical importance of Nasya with Tila Taila in the management of Nidranasha (Primary Insomnia): A case study

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Abstract

Introduction: Aging is a natural physiological process which is characterized by gradual weakening of metabolic process. Ayurveda has considered *Jara* as a natural and inevitable process as well as natural disease. One of the common problems seen in geriatric group is Insomnia which impairs cognitive and physical functioning and is associated with a wide range of impaired daytime functions across a number of emotional, social, and physical domains. Globally, the prevalence of insomnia has been reported in the range of 12%–40% in the older population aged >65 years whereas it has been reported to be 82.17% in India which is a common troubling problem in the elderly individual.

Materials and methods: A 64 years old female patient presented with disturbed sleep at night, fatigue, lack of concentration, loss of interest in day today activity for 2 years. The line of treatment focused on this case is *Nasya* with *Tila taila* 4ml each nostril for 7 days. **RESULTS:** There was a visible and significant improvement seen in sleep pattern and were assessed using Athens Sleep Questionnaire (ASQ). The ASQ shown significant improvement from 21 (Before *Nasya*) and 11 (After *Nasya*).

Discussions and conclusion: In Ayurveda *Nidranasha* which is included in 80 *Nanatmaja Vata Vikaras*. As per fundamental principles *kapha* is predominant *dosha* during childhood, *pitta* during the adulthood and *Vata Dosh* during old age. In aged the *prana* and *Udana Vata* gets vitiated which results in derangement of *Bhuddhi*, *Smritih*rasa, *Varnaviparyaya*, *Balakshaya*. *Tila Taila* has a property of *Madhura Rasa*, *Madhura Vipaka*, *Balya* and *Rasayana Karma* which is *Vataghnesha Uttam* administered as *Nasya* through Nasal route reaches *Sringataka Marma* eventually spreads in *Murdha* through micro intra cranial circulation. The Tyrosine amino acids and other essential component present in *Tila* has been directly connected to the serotonin activity of brain also in the production of Melanin which leads to improvement in Sleep and anti-aging effect on brain.

Keywords: Insomnia; *Nasya*; *Nidranasha*; *Tila Taila*

1. Introduction

Aging is a natural physiological process which is characterized by gradual weakening of metabolic process. Ayurveda has considered *Jara* as a natural and inevitable process as well as natural disease. One of the common problems seen in geriatric group is Insomnia which impairs cognitive and physical functioning and is associated with a wide range of impaired daytime functions across a number of emotional, social, and physical domains. Globally, the prevalence of insomnia has been reported in the range of 12%–40% in the older population aged >65 years whereas it has been

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reported to be 82.17% in India which is a common troubling problem in the elderly individual. In Ayurveda *Ahara, Nidra* and *Brahmacharya* are known as *Trayopastamba* which is important in maintaining the equilibrium of living were the inclusion of *Nidra* in the three *Upastambha* proves its importance. *Nidra* is defined as when the mind and body are tired then *Kapha Dosha* and *Tamasa Guna* will be increased in the body, in which sensory organs are unable to function properly. This condition leads to development of *Nidra*. As per fundamental principles *Kapha* is predominant *Dosha* during childhood, *Pitta* during the adulthood and *Vata Dosha* during old age. The vitiation of *Vata* in old age leads to *Nidranasha* is one of the *Vatananatmaja Vyadhi* described by Acharya Charaka. In this case study the presentation of *Nidranasha* (Primary Insomnia) in old age is related to *Prakopa* of *Vata* in *Shiras Sthana* and treated with principle of *Nasya Karma* for stipulated period and observations are noted.

2. Case study

- Name - XYZ
- Age - 67
- Gender - Female
- Occupation - Homemaker
- OP number - 4922/24
- IP number - 783/24

2.1. Chief complaint

Patient came to Panchakarma OPD with presenting complaints of disturbed sleep at night, fatigue, lack of concentration, loss of interest in day today activities in the past 2 years.

2.2. History of illness

Patient was apparently normal before 2 years, gradually she noticed impairment in daily sleep and loss of interest in activities.

2.3. Medical history

Previously was Under Physiotherapy treatment for Cervical pain for 1 month and recovered from the complaint.

2.4. Family history

No relevant family history noticed

Table 1 Personal history

Diet	Mixed
Appetite	Regular
Sleep	Irregular
Bowel	Irregular (Sometimes constipated)
Micturition	Normal
Habits	NIL
Addictions	NIL

Table 2 General examination

BP	120/80mmHg	NAILS	Normal
RR	16	LYMPHNODES	Normal
EDEMA	Absent	WEIGHT	74 Kg
ICHTERUS	Absent	PALLOR	Absent
PR	69	CYANOSIS	Absent

Table 3 *Ashta Sthana Pareeksha*

NADI	Vata Pitta	SHABDA	Madhyama
<i>MALA</i>	<i>Sushka</i>	<i>SPARSHA</i>	<i>Anushnasheeta</i>
<i>MUTRA</i>	<i>Alpa</i>	<i>DRIK</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>
<i>JIHWA</i>	<i>Nirlipta</i>	<i>AKRUTHI</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>

Table 4 *Dasavidha Pareeksha*

PRAKRUTI	Vata pitta	SATMYAM	Sarvarasa
<i>VIKRUTI</i>	<i>Vata</i>	<i>SATVAH</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>
<i>SARA</i>	<i>Medas</i>	<i>VAYAH</i>	<i>Vridha</i>
<i>SAMHANANA</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>	<i>AHARA SHAKTI</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>
<i>PRAMANAM</i>	<i>Avara</i>	<i>VYAYAMA SHAKTI</i>	<i>Avara</i>

3. Line of treatment

Nidranasha comes under 80 *Nanatmaja Vata Vyadhi*^[1] and *Urdhvajatrugata Vikara* Where *Vata Dosha* mainly involved, therefore medications which offer *Vata Shamaka* effect can be recommended for pacifying *Doshas*^[2]. *Nasya Karma* in this regard works greatly to facilitate transportation of drug through the nasal route. The treatment principle of *Nasya Karma* is incorporated in the case study. *Tila Taila* was selected as *Nasya Karma Aushada*, as because it possesses *Vatahara* properties. There are various references in the Ayurvedic classics which show the effect of *Tila Taila* on *Vatadosha*^[3].

Table 5 External Treatment

S.no	Procedure	Medicine	Duration
1.	<i>Nasya</i>	<i>Tila Taila 4ml/Nostril</i>	7 days

3.1. Assessment criteria

1. Athens Sleep Questionnaire (ASQ)^[4]

4. Results

After completion of *Nasya karma* on 7th day, the patient condition was reassessed. The patient's sleep pattern is improved. ASQ Scale score decreased. The patient was discharged after 7 days and condition was stable in the follow-up period of 1 month.

Table 6 Athens Sleep Questionnaire (ASQ)

Before nasya karma	After nasya karma
21	11

5. Discussion

5.1. Probable mode of action of Nasya in Nidranasha

The procedure involves *Sthanika Abhyanga* as *Purva Karma* which helps to alleviate *Vata*, this also relaxes body and mind to bring state of sleep. In classics it is suggested that oiling the head region for inducing *Nidra*. *Swedana* also

perform as *Purva Karma* to increase local circulation and facilitate maximum absorption of drug in subsequent procedure. *Pradhana Karma* which *Nasya karma* where *Dravya* instilled into the nostrils keeping patient's head in tilted position^[5,6]. A human nose has two primary functions namely respiration and olfaction, Olfactory mucosa of nasal cavity which makes the rear end of the nasal cavity is unique in the sense that it is connected to the external environment at one end and to the CNS on the other. The *Nasya Karma* facilitates drug's transportation into the brain to stimulate olfactory neurons. *Avichchhina Dhara* means a continuous flow of oil should be maintained during the procedure, *Nasya Dravya* reaches the *Shringataka Marma* - A vital point connected to the *Siras*. The drug stimulates olfactory neurons and removes vitiated *Doshas*. Stimulation of this can have profound effect on body since it connected greatly with higher centers of the brain. The olfactory nerve related to the sleep-regulating centers and hypothalamus thus induces mental calmness after receiving medication through *Nasya*^[7,8]. The drugs administered as *Nasya* penetrate and perfuse the brain cells, correct circulation of Prana, affecting cerebral and sensory center to induce sound sleep. Drugs administered through nostril acts on neurotransmitters (serotonin and dopamine) thus reduce stress and tension which are associated with insomnia. Drug when absorbed through the nasal route they reach to the vascular pathways via nasal mucosa, this process stimulates olfactory bulb and brain center to induce sleep^[9].

5.2. Probable mode of action of Tila Taila in Nidranasha

Tila Taila is an important *Vatahara Dravya*. The use of *Tila* in the form of oil can be used as *Abhyanga Shirodhara*, *Nasya*, *Basti* in *Panchakarma* therapy. The qualities of *Tila Taila* mentioned in ancient Ayurvedic books include *Madhura rasa*, *Kasaya anurasa*, *Usna Virya* and *Madhura Vipaka*, as well as *Usna*, *Vyavayi*, *Visada*, *Suksma*, *Tiksna*, *Guru*, *Vikasi*, *Lekhana*, and *Sara*. Action of *Tila Taila* mentioned in different text of Ayurveda as *Brimhana*, *Vrishya*, *Prinana*, *Medhakara*, *Sthairya*, *Varnakara*, *Tvakprasadana*, *Balya*, *Krimighna*, *Chaksusya*, *Baddhavinmutra*, *Yoni Shira Karnashul Hara*, *Chinna-Bhinna Viddha picchita Vrana*, *Abhyamaga*, *Garbhashaya shodhan* and *Loghutakarak*^[10]. Its consumption is fantastic for raising iron levels, lowering cholesterol, treating heart conditions, and boosting strength. Sesame oil is beneficial for skin. The presence of alkaloids, saponins, flavonoids, tannins, phenols, and minerals are what causes these positive impacts on health. Terpenoid presence gives antibacterial and anti-diabetic properties. Terpenoid also aid in lowering blood pressure and blood sugar levels. Alkaloids are central nervous system stimulants. Flavonoids and phenols give it antioxidant properties also saponins which are antioxidant, anti-cancer and immunity booster^[11]. As *Prakopa* of *Vata* is seen in *Nidranasha* condition where the *Vata Shamaka Dravya Tila* is used in form of *Nasya*, which is *Madhura*, *Snigdha* and *guru guna* of *Tila* help in nourishment of the *Dosha*. *Ushna Virya* and *Snigdha Guna* of *Tila* helps in pacifying vitiated *Vata Dosha* which is predominant factor in causation of symptoms of ageing. *Tila Taila* has a property of *Madhura Rasa*, *Madhura Vipaka*, *Balya* and *Rasayana Karma* which is *Vataghnesha Uttam* administered as *Nasya* through Nasal route reaches *Sringataka Marma* eventually spreads in *Murdha* through micro intra cranial circulation. The Tyrosine amino acids and other essential component present in *Tila* has been directly connected to the serotonin activity of brain also in the production of Melanin which leads to improvement in Sleep and anti-aging effect on brain.

6. Conclusion

There was a visible and significant improvement seen in sleep pattern and were assessed using Athens Sleep Questionnaire (ASQ). The ASQ shown significant improvement from 21 (Before *Nasya*) and 11 (After *Nasya*). *Nasya Karma* with *Tila Taila* can be particularly effective in treating *Nidranasha* as it enhances the bioavailability of the drug through the nasal route, thereby improving its efficacy. This therapy helps alleviate *Vata* by delivering medication through the nostrils, which stimulate olfactory neurons and improve sleep quality.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

References

- [1] Chakrapani, Charaka Samhita by Agnivesa, edited by Vaidya Jadavaji Trikamji Acharya, Chaukhambha Publications, New Delhi, Reprint 2017, Sutrasthana, 20/11, 113.

- [2] Pathak kbd. Nidra and nidranasha: a review article. Nidra and nidranasha: a review article. 2019 aug 12;(issn 2455-3301 wjpmr).
- [3] Jawanjal p. Tila taila a review. World journal of pharmaceutical and medical research. 2018 sep 9;(issn 2455-3301 wjpmr).
- [4] Haitham Jahrami, Khaled Trabelsi, Zahra Saif, Md Dilshad Manzar, Ahmed S. BaHammam, Michael V. Vitiello, Reliability generalization meta-analysis of the Athens Insomnia Scale and its translations: Examining internal consistency and test-retest validity, Sleep Medicine, Volume 111, 2023, Pages 133-145, ISSN 1389-9457,
- [5] <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sleep.2023.09.015>.
- [6] Bohra M, Shukla GD. A Comprehensive Review of Nasya Therapy in the Management of Anidra (Insomnia). Himalayan J H Sci [Internet]. 2024 Sep 15 [cited 2024 Sep 15]; 9(3):1-3. Available from: <http://www.hjhs.co.in/index.php/hjhs/article/view/211>
- [7] Maharishi Sushruta, Ayurveda Tattva Sandipika, Kaviraj Ambikadutta Shastri, Part - I, Reprint 2011, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan, Sushruta Samhita, Sutra Sthana, Chapter-4, Verse No. -32, Page No. -44.
- [8] Maharishi Sushruta, Ayurveda Tattva Sandipika, Kaviraj Ambikadutta Shastri, Part - I, Reprint 2011, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan, Sushruta Samhita, Sutra Sthana, Chapter-24, Verse No. -8, Page No. -131.
- [9] Sharma H. Kashyapa Samhita, Khilla, 5/7. 5th ed. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan; 1998, pg. 256.
- [10] Bohra M, Shukla GD. A Comprehensive Review of Nasya Therapy in the Management of Anidra (Insomnia). Himalayan J H Sci [Internet]. 2024 Sep 15 [cited 2024 Sep 15]; 9(3):1-3. Available from: <http://www.hjhs.co.in/index.php/hjhs/article/view/211>
- [11] Jawanjal p. Tila taila a review. World journal of pharmaceutical and medical research. 2018 sep 9;(issn 2455-3301 wjpmr).
- [12] The constituents of Medicinal plants, an introduction to the chemistry and therapeutics of herbal medicines, by Andrew Pengelley, first south Asian edition, 2006.